

8T – Proof: Anti Matter

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting of the 8T, author will present a proof for anti-matter using the primordial equation of coupling constants.

Introduction

The 8T is a the theory of variational curvature, the main equation (1) is describing the principle of equivalence between gravity and acceleration, and by demanding the two conditions $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ and $\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$ we have the conditions to "dark energy" which Is the result of distinct manifolds interacting in areas of extremum curvatures, leading to an acceleration from those areas, and

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^{K/2} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.42) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term of equation (1) and derived the existence of Fermions. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \tag{1.47}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \tag{1.48}$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matrix tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \tag{1.49}$$

The wave equation of the Bosonic class is represented by the wave equation, which is net curvature diverging on the matrix tensor. that is by a five-vector.

$$\left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu} \rightarrow \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_{V\mu} + (e^-)_\mu \right) + N_{V\mu}$$

$$8 \rightarrow 2^{e^-}$$

$$8 = \gamma + \mathcal{W}$$

$$F_R \# = \left((\gamma + \mathcal{W}) * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V$$

$$(\gamma + \mathcal{W}) = 2^{e^-}$$

$$(\gamma + \mathcal{W})^2 = (2^{e^-})^2$$

$$(2^{e^-})^2 = 64 = 0$$

$$(\gamma + \mathcal{W})^2 = \gamma^2 + 2\mathcal{W}\gamma + \mathcal{W}^2$$

$$2\mathcal{W}\gamma = 0$$

$$\gamma^2 + \mathcal{W}^2 = 0$$

$$[(\gamma, \mathcal{W}) > 0] \cup [(\gamma, \mathcal{W}) < 0]$$

$$\mathcal{W} \equiv e^-$$

$$[(\gamma, e^-) > 0] \cup [(\gamma, e^-) < 0]$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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